

Making music in hybrid performance settings

Miriam Akkermann

TU Dortmund

miriam.akkermann@tu-dortmund.de

Abstract

Latest since the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, creating and listening to musical performances in (online) virtual spaces have become a ‘new normal’ – at least for a couple of months. This happened against the background of both a strong tradition of in-person concerts and performances in music, i.e. performers and listeners share the same (physical) space, and a history of networked musical performances that started more than 100 years ago. Today, developments in digital technologies, especially (fast) data processing and data transmission offer a broad range of possibilities to connect distant players, sounds, and audiences. This broadens not only the possibilities of how to make music together at a distance, it also changes the sense of what is considered ‘the’ space in which music is made. Emerging constellations are often referred to as so-called ‘hybrid spaces’ – in the case of music, usually a combination of virtual and architectural (physical) spaces. In this paper, approaches to defining ‘hybrid space’ are presented and linked to a discussion on how this applies to music performances, as well as what this means for the ‘music making’.

1. Introduction

In the 20th century, a wide range of technologies – from early analog formats such as radio broadcasting to computer network music,¹ digital media and more general data transmission systems – have been developed that allow to relocate performers, sounds, visuals, and the audience. Many of the most recent constellations combine (live) video, prepared sound, and live sound production in various ways and with multiple artistic goals. In contrast, musical performances are deeply grounded in the format of in-person settings, i.e. all musicians and listeners are physically present in the same architectural space. It is hence no surprise that also new formats for musical performances seem to still share this on-site impetus, while newly developed technologies allow at the same time to explore the genuinely creative potential of real-time data-sharing in virtual spaces. This is also facilitated by the fact that one of the major challenges of networked performances, the latency in data transmission, has been limited to an acceptable minimum,² which allows to create a so-called ‘hybrid space’ for musical performances that seemingly blend real and virtual spaces in real-time.

¹ Amongst other in 1970’s with *The League of Automatic Music Composers*, and later, well-known, the ensemble The Hub (see e.g. J. BISCHOFF et C. BROWN, « History League of the Automatic Music Composers », s. d. [en ligne : http://crossfade.walkerart.org/brownbischoff/introduction_main.html] ; M. AKKERMANN, « Computer Network Music – Approximation to a far-scattered history », Berlin, 2014 [en ligne : www.ems-network.org/spip.php?article363])

² See e.g. N. SCHUETT, *The Effects of Latency on Ensemble Performance*, dans *CCRMA Department of Music*, Stanford, Stanford University, 2002 ; G. WEINBERG, « Local Performance Networks: musical interdependency

With these new settings, also new questions arise, e.g.: Does making music in hybrid spaces create new expectations towards the musical performance? Do musical actions and/or interactions change? How is the musical interaction influenced by the technical outline of the hybrid setting? And what does this mean for (the musical actions of) the individual performer? In the following, this is discussed with focus on the relationship between the musical interaction and the technical settings in use.

2. Approaches to definitions

2.1. Hybrid Spaces

Often rooted in the field of architecture, ‘hybrid spaces’ can be understood in a very general sense as versatile environments that are designed to enable different functions within a single setting. For example, as stated by Oru-Oficina de Resiliencia Urbana, “[p]ublic space can be considered as hybrid by definition [...] [as] such space is meant to be used for a simultaneous variety of functions, and there are few limits to the activities that can take place there.”³ Mina Di Marino and colleagues argue that particularly in the field of architecture and urban planning, there are many spaces that are considered multifunctional and enable various types of social interaction.⁴ In this context, ‘hybridity’ often means multifunctional, flexible, and with social functions. However, it is debatable whether this particular process of hybridization also exists without the use of digital technologies, as also pointed out by Di Marino and colleagues. In other words: this kind of hybridization is accelerated by technology. In this sense, hybrid spaces are spaces in which various socio-spatial connections take place, enabling the merging of physical and digital spaces. This chimes in with Adriana de Souza e Silva and colleagues, who emphasize in particular the combination of physical and digital spaces. In their newly published description of hybrid spaces, they focus specifically on communication spaces that are created by mobile means of communication, and that are constantly changing due to the developments in communication technologies and their resulting social interaction.

“Hybrid Spaces emerge from the blending of physical and digital spaces produced by the mobility of people communicating via mobile technologies. This articulation of Hybrid Space has influenced scholars of communication, media, mobilities, and other fields, as evidenced by our analysis of literature. Over the last two decades, however, Hybrid Spaces have morphed and adapted to our changing sociotechnical landscape.”⁵

through gestures and controllers », *Organised Sound*, vol. 10, n° 3, 2005, p. 255-266 ; Z. KURTISI, « Enabling Network-Centric Music Performances in Wide-Area Networks », *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 49, n° 11, 2006, p. 52-54 ; J. ROHRHUBER et A. DE CAMPO, « Waiting and Uncertainty in Computer Music Networks », dans *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, s. l., 2005 ; C. ROTTONDI et al., « An Overview on Networked Music Performance Technologies », *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 4, 2016, p. 8823-8843 ; GRIMM, GISO, « Interactive low delay music and speech communication via network connections (OVBOX) », *Acta Acust.*, vol. 8, 2024, p. 18

³ ORU-OFICINA DE RESILIENCIA URBANA, *Focus on Hybrid Spaces*, Forbo Flooring Systems (éd.), s. l., s. d.

⁴ Cf. M. DI MARINO et al., « Hybrid cities and new working spaces – The case of Oslo », *Progress in Planning*, vol. 170, 2023, p. 2f

⁵ A. DESOUSA E SILVA, S. W. CAMPBELL et R. LING, « Hybrid Space revisited: from concept toward theory », *Communication Theory*, vol. 35, n° 1, 2025, p. Abstract

They hereby modify de Souza e Silva's definition from 2006 concerning the point, that hybrid spaces no longer only arise from the new mobility of people who carry 'the internet' away from fixed computers and into 'other' spaces using mobile devices,⁶ but that those can now be seen as an expansion of the ecologies of connected technologies and applications that allow people to use hybrid spaces in new ways and for a variety of purposes.⁷ Even though de Souza e Silva's approach doesn't directly address musical performances, it encompasses central aspects that can also be found in music: Music in hybrid spaces expands concepts such as computer network music and interactive applications via networked infrastructures such as the internet to facilitate actions that take place simultaneously in physical and digital spaces, implying a new kind of communication. According to de Souza e Silva's examples, the development of these hybrid spaces is closely linked to a sociotechnological landscape. When applying this to music, hybrid spaces are then spaces in which physical and digital music-related activities take place simultaneously, giving possibly rise to new forms of communication whereby the elements used are based on both a music- and music-technology-related context which also incorporates common means of the current socio-technological environment.

On the one hand, this strongly reminds on debates carried out with regard to mixed music for example by Vincet Tiffon in the late 1990s, where the question of which role 'space' takes in the performance of mixed music was in focus.⁸ On the other hand, the then discussed legitimacy of (loudspeaker) concerts is today no longer a central point of discussion, while the aspect of the hierarchy exposed by a stage as well as the position of performers within a spatial setting gains new relevance (e.g., due to the rising possibilities of multiple stages and guided foci through mediated appearances) – however under a different viewpoint. The latter comes along with another predominantly performance-related question: What is considered 'live' in such a setting?

2.2. 'Live' (in) music

'Live' music is usually understood as music created in 'real-time' and on site (in front of the audience) – a constellation that arises quite naturally when musicians, their sound production, and the audience are present in the same physical space. Or, as Philip Ausländer puts it: *liveness* describes the impression that something is happening in the immediate moment in which it is experienced. It is hence no surprise that the concept of 'live' is often commonly set in contrast to 'recorded'. What is accepted as 'live' is, however, also closely linked to the use or non-use of technology as well as to the way, technology is perceived. Here, de Souza e Silva's sociotechnical landscape comes in: the technical possibilities of a respective decade – what kinds of technologies people know and are accustomed with – influences fundamentally how this technology is understood (or accepted in different contexts). This can also be seen in the field of music: on the one hand, pre-recorded music can be played back, modified, or generated in real-time and used again immediately; the distinction live vs. recording does no longer work,

⁶ Cf. A. DESOUZA E SILVA, « From cyber to hybrid: Mobile technologies as interfaces of hybrid spaces », *Space and Culture*, vol. 9, n° 3, 2006, p. 261-278

⁷ Cf. A. DESOUZA E SILVA, S. W. CAMPBELL et R. LING, « Hybrid Space revisited: from concept toward theory », *op. cit.*, p. « Connectivities of Hybrid Space: from mobile devices to networked infrastructures »

⁸ See e.g. V. TIFFON, « Espace et musique mixte », *Ars Sonora*, vol. 5, 1997 (en ligne : [http://www.ars-sonora.org/html/numeros/ numero05/05b.htm](http://www.ars-sonora.org/html/numeros/numero05/05b.htm) ; consulté le 16 janvier 2020)

neither does it open necessarily two opposing poles.⁹ On the other hand, it is often no longer possible to even directly understand the extent to which sound is generated or controlled in real-time; if (inter-)actions are perceived as something happening ‘live’ or not may hence depend rather on how the audience is judging (accepting) the technology involved and its use than on the actual traceability of the (inter-)actions.

The use of media and music technology poses, however, not only new challenges for framing the concept of liveness, it also influences the understanding of ‘interaction’ – a term that was, following Peter Merchant, researcher in political and social sciences, and Jan Van Looy, researcher in communication sciences, not often defined. Providing a brief historic overview on different definitions and classifications around the term ‘interactivity’, they date first attempts back to Henry Warren White who uses this term to describe in 1879 how atoms mutually affect one another. Merchant and Van Looy state that, in a very general sense, ‘interactivity’ stands for “an active relationship between at least two entities which can be people or objects.”¹⁰ With regard to media use, they identify, following Sally McMillan, three main relationships, all outlined within a computer- or technology-mediated environment: An interactivity between humans; between humans and documents; and between humans and systems.¹¹ For the first relationship, McMillan emphasizes the direction of communication and the level of control over the communication environment; the second focuses on the active role of the audience, e.g. interactive media as opportunities for exchanges between audiences and content creators; and the third includes the interaction between people and the computer (systems).¹² All the three relationships can be found also in musical performances using networked technologies: The technical set-up enables, restricts, and controls both the range to which performers can interfere with the overall performance set-up and control their individual devices, as well as the communication and/or an exchange of information that can take place among the performers and between performers and audience. The audience, on the other hand, perceives a mediated performance output, which means that it is necessary to actively create a mode of listening/experiencing (or intervening with) the offered output material. This mutually influences if a performance is perceived (or accepted) as ‘live’.

Looking at music in hybrid spaces, it becomes clear that the challenge of perceiving ‘liveness’ applies in particular when settings offer limited comprehensibility, e.g., with regard to the actions happening in the virtual space. Applying Merchant’s and Van Looy’s reading of McMillan to music in hybrid spaces, the technical means creating hybrid spaces can be seen as facilitating communication between humans, whereby the technology becomes a central feature that connects spaces and provides control over the communication environment. The audience needs to actively join or make sense of (one of) the hybrid space(s) that establish the performance environment. This, however, doesn’t mean that there is a direct interaction between audience and artists, but it is not possible to follow the musical performance without

⁹ See e.g. A. FÖRSTEL, S. HARDJOWIROGO et H. EGERMANN, « The Actions that Make a Musical Instrument. Exploring Club-DJing as an Instrumental Practice », dans *Proceedings of the 11th International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research*, Plymouth, 2015

¹⁰ P. MERCHANT et J. VAN LOOY, « Interactivity », dans M. L. Ryan, L. Emerson et B. Robertson (éd.), *The Johns Hopkins Guide to Digital Media*, s. I., Johns Hopkins University Press, 2014, p. 302

¹¹ Cf. *Ibid.*, p. 305 with reference to ; S. MCMILLAN, « Exploring Models of Interactivity from Multiple Research Traditions: Users, Documents and Systems », dans L. Lievrouw et S. Livingstone (éd.), *The Handbook of New Media*, London, Sage, 2006, p. 205-229

¹² Cf. S. MCMILLAN, « Exploring Models of Interactivity from Multiple Research Traditions: Users, Documents and Systems », *op. cit.*

the audience actively engaging. In consequence, this means that the hybrid setting itself requires that all humans involved – musicians, performers, and audience, somehow interact (actively or passively) with the technical setting.

3. Music in hybrid spaces

In July 2024, two concerts were presented in Berlin, focusing in particular musical works that create or use hybrid spaces within the composition's setting. All pieces were performed at the Institute for Theatre Studies, Division of Music, at Freie Universität Berlin on-site and in parallel broadcasted in a live stream online in the context of the at the symposium “(Virtual) Presence!? Musical performances in hybrid spaces”.¹³ In the following, two of the presented performances, Juan Parra Cancino's *Artifacts of not-here* (2023-2024) for networked performance, and Greg Beller's *Air Sampling #006* (2024) for spatial sampling in VR, serve as examples to discuss to what extent the specific constellation influence musical actions and/or interactions between musicians as well as with the audience that are deliberately connected to their setting in hybrid spaces. Hereby, the above outlined considerations are used as a framework for the observations.

3.1. Juan Parra Cancino - *Artifacts of not-here* (2023-2024)

Artifacts of the not-here by composer, musician, and audio engineer Juan Parra Cancino is closely linked to a concert format that emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic: the “Quarantine Sessions, A Distributed Electroacoustic Network Improvisation”, which took place every Saturday afternoon during the pandemic, connecting musicians and guests from Stanford (USA), Berlin (Germany), Ghent (Belgium), and other locations to play improvised music together. Co-funded by Chris Chafe, Constantin Basica, Henrik von Coler, Fernando Lopez-Lezcaro, Parra and Klaus Scheuermann, the sessions were broadcasted live online with audio and video feeds from each musician's location.¹⁴ Since 2022, over 100 such sessions have taken place. The improvisation-based work *Artifacts of the not-here*, which is entitled as ‘Networked Performance’ and designed to be played in a hybrid setting, follows a similar concept, but with a simpler technical set-up. For the performance on July, 18th 2024 at Freie Universität Berlin, Parra used a web socket to link the online musicians together in the browser instead of using a specifically developed environment like it was used in the Quarantine Sessions. Parra, who had set up his electronic equipment in Berlin on a small stage in front of the audience, was joined online by Johnathan Impett from Ghent (trumpet), as well as Chris Chafe (sound objects) and Brice Sonaio (double bass) from California. The four musicians – Parra also had a webcam pointed in his direction – could be seen on four slabs within the browser window which was both projected on a big screen in the concert hall and also allowed the musicians to see each other. In addition, Parra was visible for the audience in the concert hall standing on stage in front of the projection screen; the online audience saw either a camera view of the full stage or the video content only. The audio input signals of the four musicians arrived separately via the web socket at Parra's mixing desk, who created on-site a stereo-

¹³ See M. AKKERMANN (éd.), „*Virtual) Presence!? Musical performances in hybrid spaces*, Berlin, Freie Universität Berlin, 2024

¹⁴ See e.g. the announcement of the 33th Quarantine Session by C. BASICA, « Quarantine Sessions, A Distributed Electroacoustic Network Improvisation », sur *Department of Music*, 2021 (en ligne : <https://music.stanford.edu/quarantine-sessions-distributed-electroacoustic-network-improvisation-33>)

mixdown that was both audible in the concert hall via a stereo loudspeaker system and online for the musicians and in the concert's stream.

Juan Parra Cancino - *Artifacts of not-here* (2023-2024) for Networked Performance; Juan Parra Cancino (networked electronics), Jonathan Impett (networked trumpet), Chris Chafe (networked cello) and Brice Soniano (networked double bass), Berlin Juli 2024. (Picture: Akkermann)

The interaction between the musicians within the improvisation was enabled via their shared sound and the videos they saw from each other. Hereby, the level of control of the three online only musicians was limited: they could control their own sound output based on what they heard on-site as well as react on Parra's stereo-mix, but they couldn't control the full system or the final output. Parra's role included more control, as he hosted the system and was in control of all incoming audio and visual contents as well as combining them to a shared output for the audience. Yet, as with many transmission-based systems, there were some connection problems at the beginning of the performance, which showed again the relevance – and the 'agency' – of the technological system with which all musicians, and in a second order also the audience, had to deal.

The on-site audience was set in a two-folded situation, being in the (physical) room with Parra and in a virtual space with the other musicians; for the audience watching the stream, it even included one more twist with a room-in-room situation: the audience was most of the time following a hybrid setting filmed and broadcasted by online streaming. Hereby, one challenge became immediately apparent: the traceability of both sound production and interaction between musicians was strongly dependent on the technology. Due to a slight delay of the video content and the often times ambiguous sound production by the musicians, it was not always easy to understand from both audiences' perspectives who created a sound and hence to understand the ongoing musical (audible) interactions. Parra playing on stage didn't make this challenge smaller, as neither audience could see him actually playing his electronic equipment – the desk with the electronics was on a rather dark stage with no camera on top to make his actions visible. He, as all the other musicians, interacted with their music technology themselves, and then sent the respective result to the networked session. It hereby seemed as if this situation was even a bit more challenging for the on-site audience, as here the audience had to abstract from their expectations deriving from on-site only performances to a performance that is presented in hybrid space, while the online audience perceived a mediated output that matched their overall experience with the technology involved.

But even though the ‘live’ interaction was not easily traceable, the performance can be seen as interactive in McMillan’s sense. This impression was fostered by the audience’s habituation to the technology: the slight latency between sound and visuals as well as the initial challenge of getting the networked system to work referred to experiences connected to live interactions in networked settings, which provided cues for the audience to understand (and believe) that the performance was played in real-time even though the online musicians never directly interacted with the audience (Parra organized the beginning and took the applause on stage), as it met the audience’s expectations and knowledge deriving from other experiences with online performances, computer networked music, or performances in hybrid spaces

3.2. Greg Beller - *Air Sampling #006* (2024)

Air Sampling #006 for Spatial Sampling in VR, is an improvisation-based piece which was developed by Greg Beller as part of the Synekine Project, Innovation Lab, HfMT Hamburg at the Ligeti Center. In the *Air Sampling* series, Beller plays a virtual instrument that he created along his needs, and that only exists in the VR space. For performances, he combines his instrument in VR Space, which is projected at the back of the stage, with musicians playing on stage. At the performance in Berlin on July 17th 2024, Beller played in a duo together with Berlin-based pianist and improviser Eunice Martins. While Martins performed (acoustically) in real-time on stage at the grand piano, Beller performed in parallel physically on stage – parts of the stage have been mapped as the correspondence of the virtual space for the motion tracking – using the VR controller to play his instrument within the VR environment. The view of his VR Google Glass was in real-time projected on the screen behind the stage. In the virtual reality, the instrument allowed to sample, replay and alter sounds that Beller pre-recorded or that occurred live on stage and that he sampled in real-time during the performance. The sounds captured were visually placed in virtual space and could then be played back by touching their visual appearance in virtual space, which ‘inserted’ them back to the architectural space: the sounds became audible in the physical performance environment (concert hall) by Beller interacting with the sounds’ virtual visual representations whereby the way he moved through the virtual space – and hence also through the physical space on stage – controlled the sound’s processing. This allowed him to sample and play sounds in real-time, and to interact on a sonic level with the other musician on stage.

The on-site audience could see both performers physically on stage as well as Beller’s actions in virtual space. As the setting was not designed to enable a listening directly in the virtual space as another entity within the same virtual space, the online audience saw again a camera view of the stage or sometimes directly the visual Beller saw in VR as a video representation. For the resulting audio, the virtual instrument’s output was equivalent to the VR-audio output (stereo) which was amplified in the concert hall; despite this, the piano was not amplified, which was no problem for the on-site audience as the performers adjusted their volume in their sonic interaction, however, it created an imbalance for the online broadcast, as only a stereo set of microphones was used to capture the entire sound of the concert hall, but this set was situated closer to the speakers than to the piano’s resonance room; hence, the piano was not well audible in the online broadcast, but both the real and the VR-generated sounds could always be heard.

Greg Beller, *Air Sampling #006* (2024) for Spatial Sampling in VR;
Greg Beller (VR) and Eunice Martins (piano), Berlin 2024. (Picture: Akkermann)

Based on the technical setting, Beller controlled his virtual instrument while communicating by technical means; the design of the virtual instrument hereby allowed him also to sample and play back sounds created by Martins which made them enter the virtual world while she performed acoustically on stage – and in real space only. While Beller could only react on audio cues but completely control the virtual instrument, Martins could not control any part of the technical setting but could see Beller’s actions in the virtual world as well as his movements on stage; she was hence able to respond not only to the audio from the virtual space but also to his physical and virtual actions. The interaction between the musicians within the improvisation was therefore structured by different restrictions and mainly found common ground at the sonic level within the emerging hybrid space.

For the audience, the fact that they could see both Beller’s movements in physical presence on stage as well as the correspondence of his actions on the virtual instruments made the connection between his actions and the appearing sound traceable and understandable. This applied also to the interaction between Beller and Martins: For both audiences, the performance presented a hybrid space that was established by a rather classical on-site performance setting of two musicians playing side by side on stage whereby one is using a digital instrument whose interface is set in virtual space. This set-up worked without major latency, making it very easy to follow the actions in the virtual world and link it to the respective appearing sounds. At the same time, also *Air Sampling #006* included a two-folded ‘room within a room’ component, this time for both on-site as well as online audience, as the virtual space was mapped onto the stage to enable the tracking. Beller hence moved – visible for both audiences – in the real and the virtual space at the same time, while the musical interaction was only enabled by the hybrid space. Perceiving his actions in terms of making music ‘live’ was supported again by the audience’s expectations and knowledge, here, e.g., deriving from experiences with VR games or maybe also other art performances using VR.¹⁵

¹⁵ Extending the stage with virtual elements seems hereby an upcoming element, as shows e.g. one of the finalists of the AI music song contest 2025 who used a hybrid VR setting in the award show on stage (See AI SONG CONTEST, «AI Song Contest Award Show», sur *Live Stream*, 16 novembre 2025 (en ligne : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=01kZpF92wh8> ; consulté le 26 février 2026), Gantasma, 1’12’17” - 1’31’26”).

4. (Live) Interaction in hybrid spaces

Despite the highly technical setting as well as the specificities coming along with hybrid spaces, musical performances in hybrid spaces seem still to be confronted with many expectations that derive from rather acoustic settings of on-site music making. At the same time, especially the perception of whether something is 'live' or classified as such is strongly influenced by the musicians' and audiences' knowledge on and customization with the technologies involved. The latter is also important for the capability of the musicians to navigate within the hybrid space: In order to create interactions within a hybrid space, musicians have to adapt to the mediated experience and apply their musical interaction to the specific setting. In both examples, the musicians showed their capacities of making sense of the audible, which allowed them to react to what they perceived – even though what they perceived was maybe only a part of the output the audience may have experienced. It seemed as if the musicians strongly build on their own individual impression (imagination) of the ongoings in the hybrid space, abstracting from their previous experience of both on-site music making and the use of the involved technology to the most likely result. This allowed them to cover up for practical inconsistencies resulting from the hybrid setting, e.g. latency issues, visual restrictions, or volume imbalances and also to creatively deal with the different levels of control embedded in the respective technological settings. The range of (inter-)action among the musicians was hereby framed by the set-up's structure, which also influenced the level to which the audience was able to trace and understand certain processes. Yet, it is important to note that there are not necessarily natural frameworks or hierarchies within hybrid settings: in each musical work, the technical structure may create a specific kind of hybrid space, facilitate individual live/real-time interactions, and set the frame for a particular output.

While the comprehensibility of the technical means hence helps to foster an interaction among the musicians as well as a 'live' experience of the audience, each setting can create its own modes of interaction. In consequence, musicians have to individually adapt to each technical setting (again), while always facing expectations towards musical performances that are seemingly independent from the use (or non-use) of technologies. This, somehow also applies to the audience: the audience has to actively relate to each new setting in order to trace musical interactions and to follow and evaluate the (audio-visual) ongoings. The hybridity of the space in which the music is presented then sets the specific context for the evaluation of the 'liveness' of a musical performance. In this context, asking for the kinds of interaction between humans and technological systems may help to identify elements that are particularly important for a specific performance setting – and hence to discuss the relationship between a specific hybrid space and particular musical (inter-)actions. Questioning the role of technology and how it is treated and perceived within a performance can therefore open up new perspectives for reflecting on the logics that enable musical (inter-)actions – in particular – in hybrid spaces

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